

>>"THIS IS ALL FROM THE DEVIL" (comment on interview about MIMS)

Explication of the Versatility of the “Big G” diagram in MIMS 1.0¹

It isn't from the Devil, but it may disturb your zealot harmony if you're unable to translate... A Mimsical Response to the Christian Far Right

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1

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EP EMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EP EMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

Re: “Big G” being from the Devil because it is laid out to overlap the Chinese pentagram

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway

Dear Readers,

I saw this comment on the interview I did on LEAK Project², and it may be petty, but since I found it so hilarious, I had to reply.

As a Christian (Christoist or Gnostic³ to be more precise), I found it really incredibly amusing. But as a sympathizer to the sentiment that we are surrounded by attacks on faith and the Good Book⁴ I felt that it was worthy to address a fact. The goal is to bring even secular atheism into a Big G mimsical framework, without insulting. Because the Power of Numbers is not God, but within God, it becomes difficult to argue with the utility of the diagram, as it is internally verified via the Fibonacci - which the Chinese found first⁵ - and the mytho historical fact of the Death of Shamash.⁶ As for “The Lord” this is a mytho historical fact⁷ and in no way shape or form pre-determined towards anthropomorphic messiahs... unless thou wish it! In other words, the Big G obeys the Power of *Physics/Principles*, particularly the Law of Relativity⁸ and allows for various or multiform Lords... as does the Bible:

- ★ El - the giant Shamash dwarf star⁹
- ★ Elohim - the body of the Lord, its star and satellites; ie - Shang Di Huang¹⁰
- ★ YHVH - the tetragrammaton Lord (see Figure 1)
- ★ Yahweh - same, but specifically the /\\ IAO/Yao/Ywahoo sound¹¹ heard in the air as the PEM Force (*F* power) flexed the Earth’s crust and energized the Plasmaelectromagnetic Sky¹²
- ★ Jehovah= Jove = Jupiter
- ★ Christos - the Egyptian messiah prophecy¹³, related to Horus, which was (like Odin) a Jupiter fact turned Martian archetypal warrior, including the scar on cheek (like Thor)

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VMROMCfX3ZQ>

³ <https://iep.utm.edu/gnostic/>

⁴ I myself will be publishing a list of EPEMC Psalms interpretations soon.

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

⁶

https://www.academia.edu/50939161/Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thun_derbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁸

https://www.academia.edu/50804985/Trigram_Law_Bagua_Dharma_Short_document_single_page_reference

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/50912947/The_Dwarf_Star_God_Origins_slideshow

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

¹³ “The Prophecy of Christos,” M. Blackburn, 1992

Chinese Etymology 字源 Home 首页 About 汉字叔叔 Research 汉字研究

Etymology 搜索字源

Traditional in your browser 繁体字的浏览器显示: 雷

Traditional in Unicode standard 繁体字的Unicode标准: U+96F7 雷

Older traditional characters 旧繁体字/异体字: 雷

Simplified in your browser 简体字的浏览器显示: 雷

Simplified in Unicode standard 简体字的Unicode标准: U+96F7 雷

Main pronunciation 主要发音: léi

Other pronunciations 其它发音: léi, lèi

Original meaning 本义: Meaning thunder, see 雷

English senses 英语理解: thunder

Usage example 用法举例: 雷達 léi dá (radar)

Importance by frequency 常用频率: 763

Shuowen 说文解字:

Character decomposition 字形分解 [?]: Compound 雷, mutant 雷 from rain 雨 yǔ and (rem- 田 tián) from phonetic three-fields 畛 lèi. (name- thunder 雷 lèi)

Decomposition notes 字形分解说明 [?]: Not applicable.

Simplification rule 简化规则 [?]: Not applicable.

Simplification rule explained 简化规则说明 [?]: Not applicable.

Variant rule 异体规则 [?]: Not applicable.

Oracle characters 甲骨文 (21)

Q J25029	Q J25030	Q J25031	Q J25032	Q J25033	Q J25034	Q J25035
Q J25036	Q J25037	Q J25038	Q J25039	Q J25040	Q J25041	Q J25042
Q J25043	Q J25044	Q J25045	Q J25046	Q J25047	Q J25048	Q J25049

Bronze characters 金文 (9)

Q B15863	Q B15864	Q B15865	Q B15866	Q B15867	Q B15868	Q B15869
Q B15870	Q B15871					

Seal characters 说文解字的篆字 (0)

There is no known seal characters found. 没有已知的说文解字的篆字.

Liushutong characters 六书通的字 (4)

Q L31063	Q L31064	Q L31065	Q L31066

Figure 1 - Etymology for 雷 (lei, thunder)¹⁴

1. Aside from the obvious plasmaglyphics that show the sumo stomp, (earthquake means shock in Chinese, to beat means hammer),
2. and the prayer on the knees,
3. we also see the stream of energy between the 4 main realms of Yggdrasil - the world's tree
4. and the Croess X, and
5. most importantly in B15687 and L31066 we see the Great Man (GOD)
6. carrying the four maltese crosses/stars/gas giants
7. under His arms.
8. Two arms signifies the World Mountain,
9. and also the arm is the Chinese word for strength.
10. In Egyptian arm is often depicted as two hills, though a bicep has only one bump.
11. Note that Lakota and African dances often involve the Heyoka lean and stomp!

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

It is already well known the Bible made use of older Babylonian and even Sumerian traditions:

- Eden = EDIN
- Nephilim = Annunaki
- Noah = Uta-Napishti¹⁵
- Adam = ADAMU
- Heaven/Kingdom = An

So what can we do with this information? What can we translate the Big G from EPEMC towards the extremes, say atheism/secular science, Evangelism, Zoroastrianism, Hinduism, Egyptian, Chinese Sciences, Lakota Sioux, Buddhism, and Druidic Arthurianism/Star Wars (for fun).

Start with the original diagram:

Figure 2 - The "big G" diagram; credit: author¹⁶

Please note the G can be any spiral form, and spiral motifs are also worldwide motifs (see epilogue)

¹⁵

<https://www.iflscience.com/editors-blog/the-ancient-babylonian-flood-myth-that-inspired-noahs-ark-had-a-dark-twist/>

¹⁶

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

Table 1 - Big G Translations

EPEMC	Lord	Force (PEM)	Aether	Numbers	Principles
Secular	Consciousness	Unified Field	spacetime ¹⁷	mathematics	Physics
Evangelical	Jesus Christ	Ru'ach	Heaven	Numbers	The Law
Hinduism	Krishna	Prajna	Aether	"Arabic" Numerals	Dharma
Mazdaism ¹⁸	Ahura Mazda	Asha	Spenta Mainyu	1 man & wife, 3 sons 3 daughters	Daena
Egyptian	Osiris	Ka	<i>Nephthys</i> ¹⁹	Logos (order)	Maat
China	Shang Di	Tao (Dao)	Ch'i (Qi)	1,2,3,5,8,10,000	Ba Gua
Lakota ²⁰	Tunkashila	Ni	Untunktahe	iyuthapi ²¹	Wowash'ake
Buddhism	Vishnu	Karma	Anutta	Nayuta-Assamky ha	Dharma
Druidism	Ieyasu Croess	The Dragon	Heaven	Tripartite God	Magick ²²

Looking across the table, most were easy to locate, some a bit more difficult, and yet all accounted for in some shape, or form, deity or abstractification, force or field.

In other words, I am not doing anything unusual or projecting. Of course, a devout evangelical might *feel* that all these other systems, being pagan, are "from the Devil," but actually the concept of Satan has shifted quite a lot, and most evangelicals ignore the overt mystical and occult sciences contained even in the gospels, let alone in the Torah (Old Testament). See especially Jewish Magick in the books involving Moshe (Moses), and the Holiest of the Holies. There is plenty of wicca-like behavior in the Torah!

¹⁷ Or Quantum Foam

¹⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zoroastrianism>

¹⁹ Goddess of <https://www.worldhistory.org/Nephthys/>

²⁰ <https://sdpb.sd.gov/oceti/documents/LakotatermsTable.pdf>

²¹ To measure <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/54848657.pdf>

²² The 'science' of quantum reality magick is beyond this treatment.

<https://druidry.org/resources/magick-and-science> &

<https://walkingdruid.wordpress.com/2015/09/06/quantum-druidry-magic/>

Table 2 - God, Void, and Chaos (Mask/Monster motif)

EPEMC	IAO / \ GOD	Counterspace	CHAOS
Secular	Universal Source	Void/0 point	Entropy
Evangelical	Yahweh	Heaven	Hell
Hinduism	Vishnu, Atman	Brahma, Rama, etc.	Kali Durga
Mazdaism	Ahura	Angra Mainyu	Druj
Egyptian	Atum-Ra (Amen)	Maat ²³ , or Nu	Apopis/Apepis/Apep
China	Pangu	Wuji	Hundun
Lakota	Wakan Tanka (Wakǰánǰ Thánǰka) ²⁴	Skan	Heyoka Haǰ?
Buddhism	Brahma, Indra, Shiva	Shunyata	Pariyati
Druidism	Woden	Anfwynn/Avalon	<i>Morgan la Fey</i>

Again looking across the “hidden” 3 aspects of the Big G (thus 5+3=8), we see again a continual rectification of the concepts, and harmony of systems. This isn’t a surprise, for if we compare Nordic Runic Magick with Chinese with Hindu “wheel of dharma” we see the same 8 sided symbol of the synchrotron. (figures 3-6)

²³ https://www.persee.fr/doc/antiqu_0770-2817_1978_num_47_1_1885

²⁴ Or Great Mystery

<https://medium.com/@braveandthegoat/wak%C8%9F%C3%A1%C5%8B-t%C8%9F%C3%A1%C5%8Bka-how-i-learned-to-say-great-mystery-in-lakota-63bd948494b6>

Table 3 - Synchrotron Radiation Worldwide

Note the Taiji and Wheel of dharma's tridosha are unified in this famous image:

Figure 7 - Tripartite Taijitu

So if the individual should read this and perchance refer, at last, to the Bible (their own standard, and read the Book of Genesis they will read this:

“The Tower of Babel

*11 Now **the whole world had one language** and a common speech. 2 As people moved eastward,[a] they found a plain in Shinar[b] and settled there.*

*3 They said to each other, “Come, let’s make bricks and bake them thoroughly.” They used brick instead of stone, and tar for mortar. 4 Then they said, “Come, let us build ourselves a city, with **a tower that reaches to the heavens**, so that we may make a name for ourselves; otherwise we will be scattered over the face of the whole earth.”*

*5 But the Lord came down to see the city and the tower the people were building. 6 The Lord said, “If as one people speaking the same language they have begun to do this, then nothing they plan to do will be impossible for them. 7 Come, **let us go down** and confuse their language so they will not understand each other.”*

*8 So the Lord scattered them from there over all the earth, and they stopped building the city. 9 That is why it was called Babel[c]—because there the Lord confused the language of the whole world. From there **the Lord scattered them over the face of the whole earth.**”²⁵*

From this we can see that there is nothing unusual about this new science, and ancient cosmology. It is quite Biblical.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

²⁵ <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Genesis%2011%3A1-9&version=NIV>